

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE VIBRATION BEHAVIOR OF A COMPOSITE DRILL TUBE

ICCM23 International Conference on Composite Materials Belfast 2023

M. Kurkowski¹, S. Michel², J. Summa³, H.-G. Herrmann^{3,4},
D. Biermann², A. Spickenheuer¹, M. Stommel^{1,5}

¹ Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V., Dresden, Germany,

² Institute of Machining Technology, TU Dortmund University, Dortmund, Germany,

³ Fraunhofer Institute of non-destructive testing IZFP, Saarbrücken, Germany,

⁴ Chair for Lightweight Design, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany,

⁵ Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Institute of Material Science, Chair of Polymer Materials,
Technische Universität Dresden, Dresden, Germany

BTA Deep Hole Drilling

[TIBO Tiefbohrtechnik GmbH]

[ISF]

Typical applications

Plastic processing

[Techpla]

Double twin-screw
extruder barrel

Renewable energy

[BWE]

[europages]

Rotor and generator shafts

Lightweight design

[BGTB]

Aircraft landing legs

Chemical industry

[itag-celle]

High-pressure pipes

Composite Drill Tubes for BTA Deep Hole Drilling

Composite
drill tube

Drilling torque
measurement

Sensors,
telemetry

Aim of the project:

- Vibration-damping
- Weight reduction
- Structure-integrated sensors
- Hybrid connection concept

Design and Manufacture of the Composite Drill Tube

Geometry:

$d_i = 40 \text{ mm}$, $d_a = 51 \text{ mm}$, $l = 2650 \text{ mm}$

Laminate structure:

$[\pm 6_2^{CF1} / \pm 45_2^{GF} / \pm 45_2^{CF1}]$

Name	Material	Stiffness [GPa]
CF1	STS40 F13, 24K, 1600 tex (Toho Tenax)	240
CF2	Dialead K63712, 12K, 2000 tex (Mitsubishi Chemical)	640
GF	SE1200, 2400 tex (Owens Corning)	82
Matrix	Epikote MGS RIMR 935 with Epikure - MGS RIMH 937 (Hexion)	-

Bonded steel adapters with drill head

Process Parallel Vibration Measurement

Video of the rotating drill tube with sensors in drilling test

Mounting the platform and the drill tube on the drill chuck

Platform with interrogator (red) and two measuring amplifiers (white)

Results of the Drilling Tests

Steel
drill tube

Chatter marks caused
by torsional vibrations

Example images

Improved surface quality

FFT analysis over drilling depth

Amplitude of FFT (Drilling Torque) [Nm]

Process parallel
vibration analysis

Vibration damping due to composite use

How can the material damping of the composite drill tube be simulated?

Model Approach

Directional material damping

- Fibers: no damping (model)
- Epoxy resin: damping (visco-elastic)

DMA measurement on epoxy resin at 20°C

Measured natural frequency of the composite drill tube: **218 Hz**

Time-Temperature Superposition

DMA measurement:

- NETZSCH EPLEXOR 2000N
- Temperature-Frequency-Sweep
- 0.5 to 50 Hz; -80 to 90 °C

Approximation by Prony series:

$$E(t) = E_0 \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^N g_i (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}) \right)$$

Mixing the Matrix and Fiber Properties in an Abaqus User-Material

$$E'_1 = E_{1f} \varphi + E_m (1 - \varphi)$$

$$E''_1 = \frac{E_m}{(1 - \varphi)}$$

Fiber properties:
non time-dependent

Matrix properties:
time-dependent

$$E(t) = E_0 \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \right) \right)$$

Storage Modulus

$$E'_2 = \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} \frac{1 + 0.85 \varphi^2}{(1 - \varphi)^{1.25} + \frac{E_m}{(1 - \nu_m^2) E_{2f}} \varphi}$$

$$G'_{12} = G_m \frac{1 + 0.4 \varphi^{0.5}}{(1 - \varphi)^{1.45} + \frac{G_m}{G_{12f}} \varphi}$$

$$\nu'_{12} = \varphi \nu_{12f} + (1 - \varphi) \nu_m \quad \nu'_{21} = \nu'_{12} \frac{E'_2}{E'_1}$$

Loss Modulus

$$E''_2 = \frac{E_m}{(1 - \varphi)}$$

$$G''_{12} = \frac{G_m}{(1 - \varphi)}$$

$$\nu''_{12} = \varphi \nu_{12f} + (1 - \varphi) \nu_m \quad \nu''_{21} = \nu''_{12} \frac{E''_2}{E''_1}$$

Modeling of the Drill Tube in Abaqus

Plies Offset Shell Parameters Display

Make calculated sections symmetric

	Ply Name	Region	Material	Thickness	CSYS	Rotation Angle	Integration Points
1	Ply-1	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	6	3
2	Ply-2	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-6	3
3	Ply-3	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	6	3
4	Ply-4	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-6	3
5	Ply-5	(Picked)	GF_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	45	3
6	Ply-6	(Picked)	GF_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-45	3
7	Ply-7	(Picked)	GF_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	45	3
8	Ply-8	(Picked)	GF_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-45	3
9	Ply-9	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	45	3
10	Ply-10	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-45	3
11	Ply-11	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	45	3
12	Ply-12	(Picked)	CF1_UMAT	0.46	<Layup>	-45	3

t=0.46 mm

Fixed Displacement/
Rotation

Steel drill head (solid)

Composite-Shell

Torque:
Static: 300 Nm
Dynamic: 0.4 Nm

Drill head can rotate and shift in Z-direction

Results: Influence of the Loss Modulus

Variation of the loss modulus

- Fiber volume content: 55%

Laminate structure:

$[\pm 6_2^{CF1}/\pm 45_2^{GF}/\pm 45_2^{CF1}]$

Matrix material has great influence on vibration amplitude.

Results: Influence of the Fiber Angle

Variation of the fiber angle

- Variation of $\pm 45^\circ$ layers
- $\pm 6^\circ$ layers for axial load not varied

Laminate structure:

$[\pm 6_2^{CF1}/\pm 45_2^{GF}/\pm 45_2^{CF1}]$

Fiber angle influences natural frequency
but not vibration amplitude.

Results: Influence of the Fiber Material

Variation of the fiber material

- Same fiber material X in all layers
- Fiber volume content: 55%

Laminate structure:

$[\pm 6_2^X / \pm 45_2^X / \pm 45_2^X]$

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Natural frequencies depend significantly on the material. Vibration amplitude is almost the same.

Results: Influence of the Fiber Volume Content

Variation of the fiber volume content

Laminate structure:

$[\pm 6_2^{CF1} / \pm 45_2^{GF} / \pm 45_2^{CF1}]$

Increasing the fiber volume fraction from 50 % to 65 % halves the vibration amplitude.

Conclusion and Outlook

- The use of composite in deep hole drilling tools significantly reduces vibrations
- Model approach for vibration amplitude prediction presented
- Matrix material and fiber volume content influence vibration amplitude
- Fiber material and fiber orientation primarily influence the natural frequency
- Model approach must be validated experimentally
- Comparison of the numerical experiments with real drilling tests is still pending

Thank you for your attention!

Project partners:

The authors kindly thank the German Research Foundation (DFG, Project number 426328330) and the Fraunhofer Gesellschaft for the project funding.